

Eggshell-silver nanoparticles reinforcement polymer films and applications

Boniface J. Tiimob, Vijaya K. Rangari* and Shaik Jeelani,

[†]Department of Materials Science and Engineering, College of engineering, Tuskegee University,
Tuskegee, AL 36088, United States

Keywords: Polymer blends, Tensile properties, CaCO₃/Ag nanoparticles, Mechanical properties

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of different proportions of synthesized eggshell/silver nanomaterial (ES-Ag) on the structural property modification and the impartation of antimicrobial activity on 70/30 poly(butylene-co-adipate terephthalate)/polylactic acid (PBAT/PLA) immiscible blend. The ES-Ag was synthesized using a single step ball milling process, and characterized with XRD, and TEM. These results confirmed existence of Ag NPs in the interstitial spaces of the eggshell particles. The films were designed using hot melt extrusion and 3D printing for mechanical and antimicrobial testing respectively. These films were also characterized by TGA, XRD, tensile testing and antimicrobial analysis. The incorporation of ES-Ag (0.5-2.0 % content) compromised tensile properties of the blend, due to poor interaction between the matrix and the ES-Ag in the ternary systems but thermal analysis revealed improvement in onset of degradation temperature and char yield at 500 °C. Though toughness was better than that of PLA, the strength was lower but synergistic to those of PBAT and PLA. The results revealed that the PBAT/PLA/ES-Ag ternary system had properties intermediate to those of the pure polymers.

1 INTRODUCTION:

Consumer interest in high quality and safe food products, coupled with environmental concerns drives the development and study of antimicrobial biodegradable coatings, fillers and films. Edible coatings, obtained from generally recognized as safe (GRAS) materials, can potentially improve food freshness, appearance and integrity. They can be used in combination with other food preservation techniques to enhance the effectiveness of the food preservation chain [1]. Antimicrobial films and coatings have emerged as new concepts of active packaging and have been developed to reduce, inhibit, or delay the growth of microorganisms on the surface of food in contact with the package [2-6]. The use of antimicrobial packaging films to control the growth of microorganisms in food has an impact on shelf-life extension and food safety [1, 7-13]. Many organic antimicrobial agents are available and can impart antimicrobial activity in active packaging materials. Also some inorganic nanomaterials incorporated in polymers are able to alter their microstructures to improve mechanical properties while adding antimicrobial benefits to the polymer systems.

Barrier to oxygen is critical in food packaging materials, due to high sensitivity of many food products to oxidative degradation, moisture dependent microbial growth, and the need for aroma retention. The improvement in barrier properties to gases, vapors, and aromas in biopolymers make them attractive for the food protection [7]. Hence, antioxidant nanobiocomposites based on poly (Σ -caprolactone) (PCL) have been prepared by incorporating hydroxytyrosol (HT) (natural antioxidant) and nanoclay, (cloisite 30B (C30B)), to help improve the poor PCL intrinsic barrier properties. Significant improvement in oxygen barrier was realized in ternary nanobiocomposites containing C30B and 10 wt. % HT [7]. In contrast, the generation of singlet oxygen by fullerenes revealed some antimicrobial potential in packaging materials. Blends of Sc₃N@I_h-C₈₀ metallic nitride fullerene (MNF), C₆₀ fullerene with polystyrene-*block*-polyisoprene-*block*-polystyrene (SIS) were evaluated for antimicrobial activity on *S.aureus* and *E. coli*. The films provided 1-2 log, kill of both bacteria, with C₆₀ blend film showing more antimicrobial activity than Sc₃N@I_h-C₈₀ [9]. Antimicrobial activity in this material is attributed to the *in situ* generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) under white light to induce oxidative damage on the cell membranes of bacteria [14].

Silver is a known antimicrobial agent. However, this can vary based on the interactions between silver and its host materials. Hence, establishing the antimicrobial activity of silver based packaging materials is very important. One study investigated the antimicrobial activity of silver (Ag) in a film by incorporating 0.001-10 wt. % Ag ions into ethylene-vinyl alcohol (EVOH) copolymer matrix. Antibacterial activity of these films assessed on contact with apple peels and chicken breast showed low inhibition on chicken breast (< 1 log reduction); while on the apple peels total inhibition was observed with 1 and 10 wt. % Ag [8]. Beigmohammadi et al. [4] also investigated the antibacterial activity of low-density polyethylene (LDPE) packaging films incorporated with Ag, copper oxide (CuO) and zinc oxide (ZnO) NPs. Coliform counts of ultra-filtrated (UF) cheese, wrapped with the active films revealed that the coliform bacteria reduced by 4.21 log cfu/g after 4 weeks of storage, as against 1.04 log cfu/g in pure LDPE films. In addition, ammonium salt modified nanoclay (C30B)/starch (ST), Ag NPs/ST and Ag NPs/C30B/ST nanocomposites active films investigated on *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *C. albicans* showed that C30B/ST reduced microbial growth in *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, possibly due to the release of ammonium salts from C30B, which affects sensitive targets in bacteria. Also, the Ag NPs/ST and Ag NPs/C30B/ST films totally inhibited growth at contact areas with all the bacteria, due to interactions between Ag^+ and the mercapto groups of the bacterial protein. It was suggested that C30B led to bacteriostatic effect **while** films with C30B and Ag-NPs led to microbiostatic effect [15,]. In this work we have investigated the effect of nanoparticles of eggshell/Ag (ES-Ag) on the microstructure and mechanical properties of PBAT/PLA 70/30 immiscible blends. The weakness in this blend due to poor interfacial interaction between the phase separated polymers can be minimized due to the inclusion of tiny ES-Ag nanoparticles. Also, the presence of silver has the potential to impart antimicrobial activity in the film.

Materials and Methods

Extrusion of polymer blends

Figure 1, presents the single screw extruder, detail of the die zone and temperature of each zone as well as some extruded ternary biofilms. About 150 g of each of the precipitated blends containing the dispersed biocides was dried for 12 hours at 140 °F in a hopper (DRI-AIR Industries Inc., model RH5).

Fig 1. Setup of the table top extrusion machine and the biofilm products

They were then extruded using a table top single screw (19 mm diameter) extruder (Wayne SN: 8001) which is driven by 2 hp motor. Five heating zones controlled by thermostat was used to melt the mixture before extrusion, three inside the barrel and two in the die zone at set temperatures 320, 320,

320, 315 and 312 °F, respectively (shown in figure 3.3). High barrel temperature causes the polymer to melt and randomly orient the particulate biocides within the flowing matrix while the screw rotation induces high velocity in the matrix, causing immense shear force which also contributes to the random distribution of the particles. About 25-30 mm wide and 0.1- 0.3 mm thick blend specimens were extruded at a screw speed of 20 rpm and a feed rate of 4.4 g/min and collect at the sheet forming die orifice. Continuous hot molten sheet of each specimen was passed through tap water stationed at the orifice of the die to quench each blend. These blends were stored in a high vacuum desiccator (JOEL, EMDSC-U10A) and removed only when characterization is needed.

Transmission electron microscopy

Transmission electron microscope (TEM- Joel 2010) was used to determine the particle sizes and morphologies of the prepared PENP, ES-Ag, NSC and ABM. One (1) mg of each specimen was dispersed in 5 mL CH₃CH₂OH for 10 min in an ultrasonic bath and a drop of the colloidal solution was deposited on a copper grid for analysis.

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out with TA Q 500 equipment. Samples of 14 ± 0.2 mg were placed in platinum pans. An empty platinum pan was used as a reference. Each sample was heated from 30 °C to 600 °C in a 50 mL flow of N₂. A heating rate of 5 °C/min was used and the continuous records of sample temperature, mass, first derivative and heat flow were taken.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD)

XRD analysis was performed on all specimens, using a Rigaku diffractometer (DMAX 2000) equipped with Cu K α radiation, a step size of 0.02°, scan rate of 1°/min, 3° to 60° Bragg's angle of diffraction and operated at 40 kV to 30 mA.

Tensile testing

Measurement of tensile mechanical properties was done using Zwick Roell Z2.0 mechanical testing system in accordance to ASTM D 882 using a crosshead speed of 500 mm/min and 2.5 kN load cells and wedge grips. Specimens were cut from the extruded sheets of polymer systems 19 mm x 0.3mm x 120 mm. The test was conducted at 20 mm gauge length with TestXpert data acquisition and analysis software. At least 15 specimens were tested and averaged in to the reported mechanical properties.

Results and Discussion

Figure 2, shows the X-ray diffraction pattern of the synthesized ES-Ag nanomaterial. The nature of the diffraction peaks suggests that the inorganic phase is highly crystalline with crystal sizes in the nanometer range due to the broader nature of the peaks [16]

Fig. 2. XRD pattern structural analysis of ES-Ag nanoparticles

The diffraction patterns for nano engineered ES-Ag shows that the material is highly crystalline and reveals peaks due to the eggshell and silver. The diffraction pattern of the curve a show characteristic peaks of eggshell at $2\theta^\circ = 23.0, 29.4, 31.5, 36.0, 39.4, 43.2, 48.5, 56.6, 57.4$ and 60.8 , corresponding to hkl crystal planes of (012), (104), (110), (113), (202), (016), (018) and (122) for calcite and matches JCPDS Pdf # 47-1743 of standard calcite.

Fig. 3. Transmission electron micrographs of the synthesized ES-Ag

Also, the pattern shows the distinct peaks of reduced silver by the presence of silver peaks at $2\theta = 38.1, 44.2, 64.4$ and 77.3 , corresponding to (111), (200), (220), and (311) crystal planes of standard silver (JCPDS Pdf # 040783). This confirmed the reduction of silver nitrate to metallic silver particles through the mechanochemical synthesis process.

The TEM micrograph in figure 3 show dark silver particles anchored on the calcite particles with particle sizes less than 30 nm (10-15 nm). It is evident from the micrographs that the material is highly crystalline, irregular and porous. Figures (7.2 b) shows a magnified image of the crystals. The porous nature of the material suggests that it can facilitate good interactions with other materials through infiltration.

Thermogravimetric analysis

Thermal stability of PLA, PBAT and their blends systems determined by thermogravimetric analysis and the results are presented in table 1. The amount of remaining material in the various neat and different blends of PBAT and PLA polymers are used to determine the thermal stability or resistance to temperature induced degradation in a material. The incorporation of ES-Ag in the 70/30 blend led to significant improvement in the thermal stability. The following improvements were observed; onset of degradation, 7-16 °C, T_{d50} , 10-14 °C, T_{dmax} , 15 °C and residual yield of about 3-4 % from the pure blend. These improvements are due to the influenced of thermally stable ES-Ag embedded in the blend. The study of PVDF/PMMA blend revealed improved T_{onset} and $T_{50\%}$ by 10.5 and 30 °C respectively, due to the addition of 6% crystalline nanocellulose crystals [19]. Also, PLA/PHB incorporated with nanoclays, the thermal degradation temperatures were observed to have increased significantly. The increase has been attributed to a decrease in oxygen permeability due to the “crooked path” effect of the filler. Thermal degradations of PENP and PBAT/PLA/ES-Ag blend composites.

This effect delays the infiltration of oxygen and the escape of volatile degradation products. Inorganic fillers (nanoclays) have also been found to improve the char yield by about 4 % during the degradation as most of them are thermally stable [20]. This conforms to our finding with the small amount of ES-Ag material included in the 70/30 blend as depicted in the residual yields in table 1. The degradation temperature of the PLA (T_{dmax1}) in the blend was observed to have aggravated due to the inclusion of ES-Ag. This is probably due to the amorphous nature of the PLA domains serving as an avenue for permeation of volatile combustions products, and since there is no order in the PLA structure the inclusion of ES-Ag increases more disorder in its domains to accelerate combustion.

Table. 1. Thermal profiles of pure and blended PBAT/PLA polymers

Specimen	T_{donset}	T_{d50}	T_{dmax1}	T_{dmax2}	% Residue
PBAT-PLA 70/30	288.06 ±5.88	341.52 ± 0.95	307.61 ± 1.43	355.59 ± 0.11	1.17 ± 0.37
PBAT-PLA-ES/Ag 70/30/0.5	252.73 ±2.64	354.34±1.17	272.81±3.71	371.16±0.53	3.51±0.83
PBAT-PLA-ES/Ag 70/30/1.0	303.75 ±2.11	356.36±0.68	277.41±1.22	371.07±0.29	4.37±0.08
PBAT-PLA-ES/Ag 70/30/1.5	302.37 ±3.31	355.46±1.03	260.27±0.64	370.45±0.60	4.58±0.11
PBAT-PLA-ES/Ag 70/30/2.0	294.81 ±2.04	352.31±1.17	261.15±0.59	370.40±0.46	4.36±0.15

Tensile analysis

The tensile analysis of the pristine and binary blend polymer composite systems is shown in figure 5. Figure 5a is the full stress-strain curve representing the general mechanical behavior of the polymeric systems under tensile load of 2.5 KN. Whiles figure 6b is the magnified portion of a showing vividly the stress strain behavior of the blend composites which appeared masked in the full plot. The figure (5) show that PBAT is extremely tough whiles PLA is brittle. Pure PBAT/PLA 70/30 blend showed synergistic improvement in ductility (526 %) and strength (~17 MPa). The blend showed distinct yielding followed by considerable cold drawing during the tensile test, indicating significant transformation of the microstructure to favor ductile fracture due to blending. The incorporation of 0.5 to 2.0 % of the ES-Ag into the matrix of the blend reveals that the ES-Ag has no

positive reinforcement to the mechanical properties of the pristine blend. Though the ductility of the blend composites is better than that of PLA, both tensile strength and toughness of the modified 70/30 blends reduced dramatically compared to those of the pure blend.

Fig. 4. Tensile analysis of PBAT/PLA/ES-Ag blend composites (a) stress vs strain curves, (b) magnified portion of stress vs strain curves in a

This suggests that the ES-Ag could not bridge the gap created by interfacial chemical distinction which causes phase segregation between the two immiscible polymers. This contrasts the finding in many studies where property improvements have been reported with the use of nanomaterials in immiscible blends [21, 22], reactive and non-reactive compatibilization with a third component [21,22] and in composites [23,24]. This is probably so because ES-Ag do not have the texture and ability to interact well with the phase segregated blend. Particularly, the reduced silver metal is free and may not have any compatibilizing effect in the blend matrix, leading to significant compromise in mechanical properties.

CONCLUSIONS:

In this work, eggshell/silver (ES-Ag) nanoparticles were prepared through a single step ball milling process, and studied to determine its effect on the microstructure, thermal, tensile and antimicrobial properties of poly (butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT)/agro-based polylactic acid (PLA) blend. The nanostructure of the ES-Ag was determined by TEM and XRD analysis. The pure blend and composites with 0.5-2.0 % content of ES-Ag were characterized using TGA, XRD, and tensile testing. The X-ray diffraction revealed that the PLA is amorphous whiles PBAT semicrystalline, resulting in a semi crystalline immiscible blend. The tensile test showed that ES-Ag compromised the tensile properties of the blend, due to less interaction between the matrix and the ES-Ag in the ternary composite systems. The results suggest that the PBAT/PLA/ES-Ag ternary composite possessed properties intermediate to those of the pure polymers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

The authors sincerely acknowledge financial support from NSF-RISE # 1459007, NSF-CREST #1137681 and AL/NSF EPSCoR # 1158862 grants, and American Dehydrated Foods Inc. for providing eggshells.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.R. Moreira, M. Pereda, N.E. Marcovich, S.I. Roura. Antimicrobial Effectiveness of Bioactive Packaging Materials from Edible Chitosan and Casein Polymers: Assessment on Carrot, Cheese, and Salami. *J. Food Sci.* **76**, 2011, pp.54-6. DOI: 10.1111/j.1750-3841.2010.01910.x
- [2] F. Tornuk, M. Hancer, O. Sagdic, H. Yetim. LLDPE based food packaging incorporated with nanoclays grafted with bioactive compounds to extend shelf life of some meat products. *LWT - Food Sci. Technol.* **64**, 2015, pp. 540-6. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2015.06.030>
- [3] M.P. Balaguer, G. Lopez-Carballo, R. Catala, R. Gavara, P. Hernandez-Munoz. Antifungal properties of gliadin films incorporating cinnamaldehyde and application in active food packaging of bread and cheese spread foodstuffs. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* **166**, 2013, pp. 369-7. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2013.08.012>
- [4] F. Beigmohammadi, S.H. Peighambardoust, J. Hesari, S. Azadmard-Damirchi, S.J. Peighambardoust, N.K. Khosrowshahi. Antibacterial properties of LDPE nanocomposite films in packaging of UF cheese. *LWT - Food Sci. Technol.* **65**, 2016, 65, pp. 106-11. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2015.07.059>
- [5] M. Llana-Ruiz-Cabello, D. Gutiérrez-Praena, M. Puerto, S. Pichardo, J.F. Moreno, A. Baños, C. Nuñez, E. Guillamón, M.A. Cameán. Acute toxicological studies of the main organosulfur compound derived from *Allium* sp. intended to be used in active food packaging. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* **82**, 2015, 82, pp. 1-11. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2015.04.027>
- [6] P. Wen, D.H. Zhu, K. Feng, F.J. Liu, W.Y. Lou, N. Li, M.H. Zong, H. Wu. Fabrication of electrospun polylactic acid nanofilm incorporating cinnamon essential oil/ β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex for antimicrobial packaging. *Food Chem.* **196**, 2016, pp.996-1004. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2015.10.043>
- [7] A. Beltrán, A.J.M. Valente, A. Jiménez, M.C. Garrigós. Characterization of Poly (ϵ -caprolactone)-Based Nanocomposites Containing Hydroxytyrosol for Active Food Packaging. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **62**, 2014, pp. 2244-52. DOI: 10.1021/jf405111a
- [8] A. Martínez-Abad, J.M. Lagaron, M.J. Ocio. Development and Characterization of Silver-Based Antimicrobial Ethylene-Vinyl Alcohol Copolymer (EVOH) Films for Food-Packaging Applications. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **60**, 2012, pp. 5350-59. DOI: 10.1021/jf300334z
- [9] D.M. McCluskey, T.N. Smith, P.K. Madasu, C.E. Coumbe, M.A. Mackey, P.A. Fulmer, H.J. Wynne, S. Stevenson, J.P. Phillips. Evidence for Singlet-Oxygen Generation and Biocidal Activity in Photoresponsive Metallic Nitride Fullerene-Polymer Adhesive Films. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **1**, 2009, 1(4), 882-7. DOI: 10.1021/am900008v
- [10] A. Khan, T. Huq, R.A Khan, B. ; Riedl, M. Lacroix. Nanocellulose-Based Composites and Bioactive Agents for Food Packaging. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* **54**, 2014, pp. 163-174. DOI: 10.1080/10408398.2011.578765
- [11] U. Costantino, V. Bugatti, G. Gorrasi, F. Montanari, M. Nocchetti, L. Tammaro, V. Vittoria. New Polymeric Composites Based on Poly (ϵ -caprolactone) and Layered Double Hydroxides Containing Antimicrobial Species. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **1**, 2009, pp. 668-77. DOI: 10.1021/am8001988

- [12] J. Tang, Y. Song, S. Tanvir, W.A. Anderson, R.M. Berry, K.C. Tam. Polyrhodanine Coated Cellulose Nanocrystals: A Sustainable Antimicrobial Agent. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **3**, 2015, pp. 1801-809. DOI: 10.1021/acssuschemeng.5b00380
- [13] D. Wang, W. Xu, G. Sun, B. Chiou. Radical Graft Polymerization of an Allyl Monomer onto Hydrophilic Polymers and Their Antibacterial Nanofibrous Membranes. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **3**, 2011, pp. 2838-44. DOI: 10.1021/am200286a
- [14] S. Rajesh, E. Koshi, K. Philip, A. Mohan. Antimicrobial photodynamic therapy: An overview. *J. Indian Soc. Periodontol.* **15**, 2011, pp. 323-7. doi: 10.4103/0972-124x.92563
- [15] A.S. Abreu, M. Oliveira, A. de Sá, R.M. Rodrigues, M.A. Cerqueira, A.A. Vicente, A.V. Machado. Antimicrobial nanostructured starch based films for packaging. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **129**, 2015, pp. 127-34. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2015.04.021>
- [16] V. Apalangya, V.K. Rangari, B. Tiimob, S. Jeelani, T. Samuel. Development of antimicrobial water filtration hybrid material from bio source calcium carbonate and silver NPs., *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **295**, 2014, pp. 108-14. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2014.01.012>
- [17] L. Jiang, M.P. Wolcott, J. Zhang. Study of Biodegradable Polylactide/Poly (butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) Blends. *Biomacromolecules*, **7**, 2006, pp.199-207. DOI: 10.1021/bm050581q
- [18] T. Lebarbé, E. Grau, B. Gadenne, C. Alfos, H. Cramail. Synthesis of Fatty Acid-Based Polyesters and Their Blends with Poly(l-lactide) as a Way To Tailor PLLA Toughness. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **3**, 2015, pp. 283-92. DOI: 10.1021/sc500648g
- [19] Z. Zhang, Q. Wu, K. Song, S. Ren, T. Lei, Q. Zhang. Using Cellulose Nanocrystals as a Sustainable Additive to Enhance Hydrophilicity, Mechanical and Thermal Properties of Poly (vinylidene fluoride)/Poly (methyl methacrylate) Blend. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **3**, 2015, pp. 574-82. DOI: 10.1021/sc500792c
- [20] P.J. Jandas, S. Mohanty, S.K. Nayak. Morphology and Thermal Properties of Renewable Resource-Based Polymer Blend Nanocomposites Influenced by a Reactive Compatibilizer. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2**, 2014, pp. 377-86. DOI: 10.1021/sc400395s
- [21] V. Ojijo, S.R. Sinha, R. Sadiku. Toughening of Biodegradable Polylactide/Poly (butylene succinate-co-adipate) Blends via in Situ Reactive Compatibilization. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **5**, 2013, pp. 4266-76. DOI: 10.1021/am400482f
- [22] J.P. Mofokeng, A.S. Luyt. Dynamic mechanical properties of PLA/PHBV, PLA/PCL, PHBV/PCL blends and their nanocomposites with TiO₂ as nanofiller. *Thermochim Acta*, **613**, 2015, pp. 41-53. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2015.05.019>
- [23] T.A. Hassan, V.K. Rangari, S. Jeelani. Value-Added Biopolymer Nanocomposites from Waste Eggshell-Based CaCO₃ NPs as Fillers. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2**, 2014, pp. 706-717. DOI: 10.1021/sc400405v
- [24] B.J. Tiimob, V.K. Rangari, S. Jeelani. Effect of reinforcement of sustainable β-CaSiO₃ NPs in bio-based epoxy resin system. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **131**, 2014. pp. 40867-4071 DOI: 10.1002/app.40867